

USER-CENTERED WORD GAME-BASED STRATEGIES IN TEACHING SCIENCE AND MATHEMATICS IN RELATION TO PUPILS' LEARNING ACHIEVEMENTS

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User-Centered Word Game-Based Strategies in Teaching Science and Mathematics in Relation to Pupils' Learning Achievements

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Abstract

The study attempted to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning achievements and the extent of utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics among Grade 6 pupils. This study also utilized the descriptive-correlational research and the Statistical tools used in the study were the mean and standard deviation to determine the extent of utilization of user-centered word game-based approach to teaching in Science and Mathematics and frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine the level of pupils' learning achievements. Pearson r was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning achievements and the extent of utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics. Findings revealed that teachers "Highly Utilized" the user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics and many of the pupil-respondents, that is 81 or 31% out of 160 respondents had an "Outstanding" learning achievements while only 3 or 2% were rated "fairly satisfactory". Further, result suggests that user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics had "low or slight correlation" to pupils' learning achievements. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Subsequently, it was recommended that in teachers should be inspired to continuously design, develop, and utilize their strategic intervention materials which are responsive to pupils' inclusive and individual learning needs to improve their learning performance.

Keywords: *user-centered, word game-based, approach in teaching, pupils' learning achievement*

Introduction

The advent of technology has made learning more interactive and engaging to students especially in science subjects. This is in line with the K to 12 curriculum of the Department of Education (DepEd) which is anchored on the tenet "Learning is Fun" with an ultimate goal of making education interesting and relevant through the integration of technology in teaching environments.

The integration of technology in education makes teaching and learning more dynamic and meaningful to public school learners especially in Science and Mathematics which include abstract phenomena and concepts. The use of user-centered game-based learning provides a more effective science and math teaching in the Philippine classroom environment.

The framework of this study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to DepEd Order No. 21, series of 2019 in which the Philippine government has made explicit their agenda for integration of the 21st century skills into the education and in which it specifies that the Enhanced Basic Education Program must equip students with lifelong learning skills while simultaneously requiring that the curriculum must use "pedagogical approaches that are constructivist, inquiry-based, and experiential that expose student to learning by doing through game-based instruction.

Additionally, the study is also anchored on to section 10 of Article XIV of the Philippine Constitution and Sections 1 and 2 of Republic Act 10844 which institutionalize the integration of information technology in the Philippines and mandates that "science and technology is essential for national development and progress; the state shall give priority to research and development, invention, innovation, and their utilization; and the integration and use of information technology resources in public elementary and secondary schools in the Philippines for the purpose of improvement in teaching and learning processes.

The difficulty in teaching and learning more abstract and theoretical concepts in science has become easier through the use of user-centered game-based and assisted instruction via user-centered game-based platform or learning tools having different design structures to provide more effective learning environment (Ruiz, 2021).

Subsequently, another advantages in using user-centered game-based learning is related to students' intrinsic motivation to learn because it enhances engagement in classroom performance tasks which positively influence learning performance while playing a user-centered word-games applications (Libradilla, 2020).

Further, it was exemplified by Teves (2020) that using a user-centered word game-based educational technology and application in mobile phones and other electronic gadgets are advantages especially in Science and Mathematics classrooms. Technology has changed education several ways and the best of all is that it has made education easily accessible when compared to the traditional Science and Mathematics practice in teaching-learning.

The use of game-based teaching-learning has gained wide acceptance because technology has its foot in almost every ingredient of human's life especially the millennials and the booming growth of new technologies has helped learners to learn more easily,

effectively, methodically and most importantly it has enabled the uses to learn with more comfort which in turn helps in better understanding.

The use of educational games such as user-centered word game-based approach as learning tool is found to support the development of students' cognitive, motivational, emotional and social outlook (Ruiz, 2021). However, they are better suited to smaller classrooms with elementary and high school students rather than university students who have to achieve specific learning outcomes through course work delivered in medium to large lectures.

Early use of game-based and gamification elements in teaching science and math appeared to improve student response in academic activities with promising outcomes but researches conducted by Wang, et al (2020) revealed that there was limited impact on student engagements and motivation to perform better in academic activities especially in Science and Math.

The use of user-centered word game-based teaching-learning approach will allow elementary school pupils to overcome boredom of listening to teachers' lecture on difficult Science and Math concepts because it challenges them with audio-visually stimulating environments.

Subsequently, it was believed that can learn better in a technologically-driven environment (Mayer, 2021). This claim is based on the fact that pupils learn better in the game-based learning environment because games can enhance positive classroom dynamics and improve pupils' interactions with their peers and teachers.

The use of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics is said to influence learners' cognitive system, such as the enabling effect, and the facilitating effect. The enabling effect reduces learning time and cognitive load, while the facilitating effect allows learners to manipulate pictures which are different from static pictures for better understanding of a more theoretical and abstract materials.

The use of user-centered word game-based approach in learning Science and Mathematics is beneficial to learners because it has the multiple modes of which effectively match with the learners' various intelligence preference (Gardner, 2019). Therefore, this game can be adopted in the classroom as facet of instruction together with other instructional technology to enhance and facilitate learning.

However, the utilization of user-centered word game-based learning material as a new pedagogical trend is very limited in the public schools. There are teachers in science and math who do not utilize technology because they are more comfortable with their teaching methods while others claimed that the resources are not available for teachers' use.

It is based on the aforementioned circumstance that, the researcher is motivated to conduct a study to investigate the influence of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics and ascertain its influence to pupils' learning achievements.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the influence of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Math and Pupils' learning achievements in North City Central School Elementary School Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2023 - 2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics among Grade 6 pupils?
2. What is the level of Grade 6 pupils' learning achievements using the user-centered word game-based approach in Science and Mathematics when they are categorized as:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory; and,
 - 2.5. did not meet expectations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning achievements and the extent of utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the

analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adopted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Grade 6 pupils of North City Central School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro. There were hundred and sixty-nine (169) Grade 6 pupils of the study who answered the survey questionnaire on user-centered word game-based approach in learning Science and Mathematics. The respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire adapted from Ruiz (2021) who conducted a study on user-centered game-based its impact on students' academic performance. The survey instrument is composed of two (2) major components. The first component is on the user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics with twenty (20) indicators. Part 2 is on the pupils' learning achievements which are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission shall be asked by the researcher from the parents of Grade 6 pupils to permit the researcher to use the pupils as subject-respondents of the study. However, the parents assured that the data gathered from the survey questionnaire be treated to its highest confidentiality and be used for educational purposes only.

After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were utilized in the study;

Problem 1. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the extent of user-centered word game-based approach in learning Science and Mathematics.

Problem 2. Frequency counts and percentages were used to present the level of pupils' learning achievements.

Problem 3. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning achievements and the extent of user-centered word game-based approach in learning Science and Mathematics.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on the utilization of user-based word game based strategies in teaching science and mathematics in relation to pupils' learning achievements. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the results of a survey questionnaire in lieu of the problems presented.

Problem 1. What is the extent of the utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics among Grade 6 pupils?

User-centered word game-based teaching approach is an inordinate way to improve young learners' creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. It is based on the use of imagination. Teachers can provide pupils the self-determination to come up with elucidations which boost their level of resourcefulness. The utilization of user-centered word game-based method in teaching is an all-inclusive approach to facilitate pupils' learning and mastery of the basic concepts in Science and Mathematics. Table 1.1 presents the mean distribution of the extent of utilization of user-centered word game-based teaching approach.

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of the user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics. Overall, the respondents rated all the indicators as "Highly Utilized" with a mean of 3.85 (SD=.899). This indicates that teachers extremely utilized the user-centered word game-based teaching in Science and Mathematics. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers provided a well-designed game and supporting materials in teaching Science and Mathematics subjects to make learning more relevant, interesting, and engaging and by also allowing learners to take an active participation and assume different roles which make learning more rewarding and meaningful.

Martin, et al (2020) averred that utilization of game-based teaching in Science and Mathematics provides meaningful learning experiences to students because they are required to participate, interact, and engage which, accordingly, interactivity in games promotes and increases learning performance.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of User-Centered Word Game-Based Approach in Teaching Science and Mathematics

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Word game-based learning approach simplifies learning of Science and Math concepts.	4.91	.296	Very Highly Utilized
2. Word game-based learning materials are stimulating and engaging.	4.90	.332	Very Highly Utilized
3. Word game-based learning materials are seemingly difficult to perform.	4.77	.488	Very Highly Utilized
4. Word game-based learning approach is aligned to learning objectives.	4.60	.646	Very Highly Utilized
5. Word game-based approach recognized the value of games for learning.	4.36	.756	Very Highly Utilized
6. Word game-based approach introduces games that are simple and easy to engage.	4.04	.856	Highly Utilized
7. Word game-based learning is aided by computer or software application.	3.75	.938	Highly Utilized
8. Word game-based learning stimulates pupils' interest.	3.48	1.002	High Utilized
9. Word game-based learning material is highly accessible.	3.25	1.033	Moderately utilized
10. Word game-based learning activity permits pupils make decisions.	2.93	.144	Moderately Utilized
11. Word game-based learning activity allows pupils to develop cognition	2.65	1.336	Moderately Utilized
12. Word game-based learning activity allows pupils to remember, recall, analyze, evaluate, and create	2.82	1.541	Moderately Utilized
13. Word game-based learning material allows pupils to learn meta-cognitive and procedural knowledge	4.36	1.281	Very Highly Utilized
14. Word game-based learning material utilizes dice, board characters and board games where science and math concepts are learned.	4.36	1.281	Very Highly Utilized
15. Word game-based learning is perceived to be useful and informative	4.51	.786	Very Highly Utilized
16. Word game-based learning material is perceived ease-of-use.	4.31	.786	Very Highly Utilized
17. Word game-based learning material is perceived to develop proper attitude towards usage.	3.87	.963	Highly Utilized
18. Word game-based learning material is believed to improve learning performance	3.49	1.015	Highly Utilized
19. Word game-based learning materials teach to improve critical thinking skills.	3.13	1.198	Moderately Utilized
20. Word game-based learning materials teach propositional logic and enhance verbal skills.	2.55	1.316	Less Utilized
Overall Mean	3.85	.899	Highly Utilized

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Utilized/3.41-4.20 Highly Utilized/2.61-3.40 Moderately Utilized/1.81-2.60 Less Utilized/1.00-1.80 Not Utilized

The indicator which states that “Word game-based learning approach simplifies learning of Science and Mathematics concepts” obtained the highest mean of 4.91 (SD=.296) which is verbally described as “Very Highly Utilized”. The result indicates that teachers had developed and utilized the word game-based learning approach in order to simplify the teaching of difficult concepts in Science and Mathematics.

Ruiz (2021) asserted that difficult concepts in Science and Mathematics can be taught in most simple and easy way through game-based and learner-centered teaching. Additionally, it was emphasized that the difficulty in teaching and learning more abstract and theoretical concepts in science has become easier through the use of user-centered game-based and assisted instruction via user-centered game-based platform or learning tools having different design structures to provide more effective learning environment.

The use of game-based teaching-learning has gained wide acceptance because technology has its foot in almost every ingredient of human's life especially the millennials and the booming growth of new technologies has helped learners to learn more easily, effectively, methodically and most importantly it has enabled the users to learn with more comfort which in turn helps in better understanding.

The use of educational games such as user-centered word game-based approach as learning tool is found to support the development of students' cognitive, motivational, emotional and social outlook. However, they are better suited to smaller classrooms with elementary and high school students rather than university students who have to achieve specific learning outcomes through course work delivered in medium to large lectures.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.55 (SD=1.316) is verbally described as “Less Utilized” in the indicators “Word game-based learning materials teach propositional logic and enhance verbal skills”. The result implies that teachers infrequently or rarely utilized word game-based learning materials to pupils that teach how meanings of words and its inferential relationship or connection with each other. It can also be inferred based on findings that teachers do not emphasize the development of pupils' verbal skills because the game-based teaching focuses only on the mastery of basic competencies in Science and problem-solving for Mathematics.

The use of user-centered word game-based approach in learning Science and Mathematics is beneficial to learners because it has the multiple modes of which effectively match with the learners' various intelligence preference (Gardner, 2020). Therefore, this game can be adopted in the classroom as facet of instruction together with other instructional technology to enhance and facilitate learning.

Problem 2. What is the level of Grade 6 pupils' learning achievement using the user-centered word game-based approach in Teaching Science and Mathematics when they are categorized as: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectation?

Pupils' learning achievements is measured in terms of mastery of the learning competencies and the development of essential skills required for success in academic activities. Academic achievements are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations. Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of pupils' learning achievements.

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution of Pupils' Learning Achievements*

<i>Pupils' Learning Achievements</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	81	31%
Very Satisfactory	29	18%
Satisfactory	40	25%
Fairly Satisfactory	3	2%
Did not meet expectation	7	4%
Total	160	100%

As seen, 81 (31%) of Grade 6 pupils were rated “Outstanding” in their learning achievements. This means that there were more pupils who performed exceptionally in their academic activities. Thus, it is imperative for teachers to utilize user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics. Sanchez (2021) asserted that word game-based learning approach creates a meaningful connection to pupils’ engagements in learning, mental activity, social interactions, and academic success.

On the contrary, 3 (2%) of the pupil-respondents manifest “Fairly Satisfactory” learning achievements. This implies that only few Grade 6 pupils achieved equitably and reasonably in Science and Mathematics. It can be inferred that the use of game-based teaching approach has improved pupils’ academic performance. Thus, only 2 out of 160 Grade 6 pupils achieved fairly satisfactory (Grades from 75% to 79%) in Science and Mathematics.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils’ learning achievements and the extent of utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics?

Table 3 presents the test of relationship between the pupils’ learning achievements and the utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics.

Table 3. *Test of Relationship between Pupils' Learning Achievements and Utilization of User-Centered Word Game-based Approach in Teaching Science and Mathematics*

		<i>Pupils' Learning Achievements</i>		
(r)	Sig 2-tailed	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1	
.113	.379	Signifies Low or Slight correlation	Rejected	

**significant at p<0.05 alpha level*

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between pupils’ learning achievements and the utilization of word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics. Results revealed that the utilization of word game-based approach signifies low or slight correlation to pupils’ learning achievements ($r=.113$) as indicated in the significant value of .379. This result indicates that the utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics negligibly or slightly affect pupils’ learning achievements. Thus, null hypothesis which states that “there is no significant relationship between pupils’ learning achievements and the utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics” is rejected. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils’ learning achievements can be attributed to the utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics. This finding was in congruence to the findings of Sanchez (2022) who suggests that game-based approach in teaching helps develop pupils’ learning achievements and school performance.

Bodrova and Leong (2020) pointed out that user-centered word game-based approach is teaching Science and Mathematics subjects were found to be meaningful, joyful, actively engaging because it builds upon itself, and socially interactive which contribute to pupils’ learning achievements.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Children predictably learn through the utilization of an approach in teaching that encourage pupils’ participation and engagement. The user-centered word game-based approach in teaching in Science and Mathematics classes promotes learning engagements among grade 6 pupils and eventually contribute to an improved learning achievements. This learning approach contributes to improve young learners’ creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.

Pupils’ learning achievement is measured in terms of their academic and learning achievements which is usually described based on their grades. Pupils’ learning achievements is influenced by different factors such as pupils’ cognitive and mental readiness, motivation to learn, and most importantly the approaches and teaching strategies utilized by teachers to teach difficult concepts more easy and simple.

Every teacher dreams of improving pupils’ learning performance through the utilization of functional teaching approaches and the use of intervention materials to achieve and master the desired learning competencies. Teachers’ utilization of user-centered word game-based approach in teaching Science and Mathematics to improve learning and academic performance. Moreover, teachers’ ingenuity in designing appropriate user-centered word game-based approach in teaching is evocative of pupils’ motivation to engage in learning

activities.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will be aware of teachers' ingenuity and creativity in designing an instructional intervention to promote pupils' learning performance. The results of the study may inspire the officials of the Department of Education to provide incentives to teachers who use their creativity in crafting intervention materials for the least mastered competencies and to address the special learning needs of the public school learners.

School Principals/School Heads will inspire teachers to develop their strategic intervention materials to address pupils' learning needs. The intervention materials should be the results of research on inclusive needs of pupils and the crafted should be evaluated and properly packaged for utilization.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to continuously develop their strategic intervention materials which is user-centered to address the inclusive needs of their learners in order to improve academic and learning performance.

Parents are recommended to always provide the needed support in their children's learning activities and ensure parent-teachers collaboration in the education of their children. They are also enjoined to provide an inclusive support to their children's education through the provision of learner-centered home school learning environment.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders are recommended to always support and provide the needed logistical assistance to the school especially in the utilization available community resources.

Future Researchers are encouraged to conduct a similar investigation that thoroughly explore the functionality and utilization of user-centered word game-based intervention learning materials in order to validate the findings of this investigation and at the same time motivate teachers to continue their advocacy of developing, designing, and utilizing intervention materials to improve pupils' learning achievements.

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